

Highly Enantioselective Conjugate Additions of Aldehydes to Vinyl Sulfones

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Given the reach chemistry of the aldehyde and the sulfone groups,^[1] merging both functionalities through stereoselective C–C bond-forming reactions is highly appealing. Towards this goal, the 1,4-addition of aldehydes to unsaturated sulfones is a highly valuable tool. Unfortunately, catalytic and enantioselective variants of the reaction are seemingly elusive.^[2] First reports of catalytic enantioselective conjugate addition of aldehydes to vinyl sulfones involve secondary/tertiary 1,2-diamine organocatalysts **1** and **2**,^[3] which activate the aldehyde component through enamine formation.^[4,5] The behaviour of these catalysts is significant, but the method holds important limitations with regard substrate scope and enantioselectivity: a large excess (10 equivalents) of the aldehyde is usually required and modest selectivity (typically 70% *ee*) is produced. On the other hand, while the direct catalytic and asymmetric 1,4-addition of aldehydes to certain electron deficient olefins,^[6,7] most particularly nitroolefins, ^[7,8] have met success recently, one accompanying problem to the reaction with vinyl sulfone acceptors is retroaddition, which causes formation of undesired dimeric side-products.^[3] The finding we report here is that the use of less basic chiral amine catalysts provide a solution to these problems thus expanding considerably the utility of vinyl sulfones in organic synthesis.

In an initial screen, commercially available prolinol silyl ethers **3** and **4**,^[9] and the analogue **5**, recently disclosed from our laboratory,^[10] were tested for the reaction between aldehydes **6** and vinyl bis(sulfone) **7**. At the outset, it was not clear whether

each catalyst would be equally effective. Besides the above problems, there is the fact that diaryl prolinol ethers may exhibit certain substrate specificity.^[11]

Figure 1. Amine catalysts explored for the conjugate addition of aldehydes to vinyl sulfones. (a) previous studies; (b) this work.

Table 1. Addition of aldehydes **6** to vinyl sulfones promoted by **3**

Aldehyde 6 , R	Sulfone	Product	Yield [%] ^[a]	syn/anti ^[b]	ee [%] ^[c]
a CH ₃	7	10a	95	--	95
	8	11a	60	85:15	99(99) ^[d]
b CH ₃ CH ₂	7	10b	93	--	98
	9	12b	49	70:30	99(ND)
c CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂	7	10c	94	--	97
d CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₃	8	11d	52	70:30	99(99) ^[d]
	9	12d	51	70:30	99(ND)
e CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄	7	10e	95	--	96
f PhCH ₂	7	10f	92	--	95
g (CH ₃) ₂ CH	7	10g	91	--	99

[a] Isolated yield of product alcohol after column chromatography (hex:EtOAc 60:40). [b] Determined by ¹H/¹³C NMR and chiral HPLC. [c] Determined by chiral HPLC. [d] *ee* of the minor diastereomer. ND: not determined.

To our delight, Table 1, by using catalyst **3**, products **10** were obtained, after reduction of the 1,4-addition adduct, in yields typically over 90% and enantioselectivities greater than 95% for both linear as well as β-branched aldehydes. For example, propionaldehyde, which provides racemic adducts with catalyst **1**, affords **10a** with 95% *ee*. Similarly, valeraldehyde affords **10c** with 97% *ee*, whilst only 54% *ee* is attained with catalyst **1** (74% *ee* with **2**). Among the solvents examined methylene chloride and

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toluene were the best. No reaction was observed in protic solvents like ethanol, methanol or isopropyl alcohol, whilst in DMF, a typical solvent for other enamine based reactions, low *ee*'s are produced. Catalyst **4** behaved similarly, but **5**, which performs very well in other 1,4-addition reactions,[10] gave rise to products of 60%–75% *ee* at best.[12] Formation of dimeric side product was determined to be below the limit of detection of ¹H NMR in all cases. On the other hand, β-substituted sulfones **8** and **9** were also competent electrophiles for this reaction, giving rise adducts **11** and **12** with good yields, diastereomeric ratios in the range from 70:30 to 80:20, and essentially complete enantioselectivity.[13]

Table 2. Aldehyde addition to *E*-α-ethoxycarbonyl vinyl sulfones promoted by **3/4**

Product 16		Cat.	Time [h]	Yield [%] ^[b]	dr ^[c]	<i>ee</i> [%] ^[d]	
R	R ¹						
a	Me	Ph	3	3	85	80:20	99
			4	3	54	80:20	98
b	Me	2-naphthyl	3	3	75	75:25	97
c	Pr	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	3	20	60	75:25	99
			4	20	30	70:30	97
d	Pn	Ph	3	16	78	75:25	98
			4	16	35	75:25	ND

[a] Reactions conducted at 0.5 mmol scale in CH₂Cl₂ at r.t. overnight. Aldehyde:vinylsulfone 3:1 ratio. [b] Isolated yield of lactone product after column chromatography (Hex/EtAcO 90:10). [c] Determined by ¹³C NMR; relative and absolute configuration of the minor diastereomer not determined. [d] Determined by chiral HPLC. ND: not determined.

The present catalytic reaction can also be applied to other vinyl sulfones with maintained levels of stereoselectivity. For example, as shown in Table 2, α-ethoxycarbonyl vinyl sulfones **13**, **14**, and **15** reacted with aldehydes in the presence of catalysts **3/4** (10 mol%) to give, after reduction and cyclisation, the corresponding lactone adducts **16** with three contiguous stereocenters. Nearly perfect enantiocontrol is observed in most cases with both the catalyst, but catalyst **3** provided better yields (up to 85% yield over three steps) than **4**. It is particularly noteworthy the fact that the sulfone group is key for the 1,4-addition reaction to proceed satisfactorily. For instance, whilst vinyl sulfones **13a** and **13c**, upon reaction with propanal and pentanal, respectively, afforded products **16a** and **16c** in 85% and 60% yield, the respective arylidene ethyl malonates, which would generate analogous δ-lactones, were unreactive regardless the reaction conditions employed.[14] In this respect, δ-lactones are common structural units of natural products as well as versatile building-blocks of several classes of biologically active compounds.[15]

A third variation concerns α,β-unsaturated nitriles, a recalcitrant class of Michael acceptors[16] that remain completely unreactive under the present catalytic conditions. However, addition of aldehydes to α-cyano vinyl sulfones **17–20** took place smoothly at –40 °C (Table 3) to give, after reduction of the resulting adduct, alcohols **21**. The latter compounds are versatile intermediates which allow, for example, access to lactones **22** or cyano alcohols **23** in good yields, diastereomeric ratio, and again essentially perfect enantioselectivity. This approach constitutes a new

enantioselective entry to building-blocks otherwise difficult to access from unsaturated nitriles.[16] In the above reactions a threefold excess of aldehyde substrate is employed regularly, but nearly equimolar amounts suffice for achieving equal efficiency. Configuration of the products was established by X-ray analyses of *syn*-**12b**, **16a**, and *trans*-**22b**,[17] and by assuming a uniform reaction mechanism.[18]

Table 3. Addition to *E*-α-cyano vinyl sulfones promoted by **3**^[a]

Compound		Product 22		Product 23				
R	R ¹	Yield ^[b] [%]	dr ^[c] <i>trans/cis</i>	Yield ^[b] [%]	dr ^[c] <i>syn/anti</i>	<i>ee</i> ^[d] [%]		
a	Me	Ph	57	75:25	99(99)	70	75:25	99(98)
b		4-ClC ₆ H ₄	59	80:20	99(99)	--	--	--
c		4-MeC ₆ H ₄	65	80:20	99(ND)	70	75:25	99(97)
d		2-Naphthyl	65	70:30	99(99)	52 ^e	80:20	99(90)
e	Et	Ph	65	70:30	99(99)	65	60:40	99(99)
f	Pr	Ph	72	70:30	99(99)	70	85:15	99(ND)
g	Bu	Ph	70	75:25	99(99)	--	--	--

[a] Ratio of aldehyde/vinyl sulfone 3:1. [b] Combined yield of diastereomers over the three steps. [c] Determined by ¹H NMR and/or HPLC. [d] Determined by HPLC. *ee*'s in bracket refer to the minor diastereomer *cis*-**22** and *anti*-**23**, respectively. ND: not determined.

The potential of this catalytic methodology can be further shown by the reductive double desulfonation of **10f** and *syn*-**11d** to afford alcohols **24** and **25**, Scheme 1. This achievement represents a formal catalytic enantioselective α-alkylation of aldehydes with secondary alkyl halides, a process that still bears considerable challenge.[19] When the desulfonation step is preceded with a prior alkylation reaction under standard conditions, as in the transformation of **10f** into alcohols **26**, the above approach serves to access to longer chain alkylated products in a practical way. These examples demonstrate how the present organocatalytic conjugate addition to vinyl bis-sulfones, in conjunction with a subsequent alkylation step, opens up new opportunities for the asymmetric synthesis of α-branched aldehydes and products thereof.

Scheme 1. Elaboration of adducts via desulfonation/alkylation standard protocols.

In summary, although further optimization is needed to improve reaction diastereocontrol,[20] the present catalytic system introduces an operationally simple protocol for accessing a variety of structural motifs from readily available vinyl sulfones and unmodified aldehydes as starting materials. The trick of success is the use of a diaryl prolinol silyl ether as reaction promoter that leads to the highest enantioselectivity reported to date for this class of Michael acceptors. Further investigation on the utility of gem-disulfone adducts as alkyl carbanion surrogates are underway in our laboratory and will be reported in due course.

Experimental Section

Catalytic conjugate addition of aldehydes to vinyl sulfones: to a mixture of the respective catalyst **3** or **4** (10–20 mol%) and vinyl sulfone (1 mmol) in 1 mL of toluene (for sulfones **7–9**) or CH₂Cl₂ (for **13–15** and **17–20**) at –40 °C was added aldehyde **6** (1.5–3.0 equiv.), and the mixture stirred overnight (16 h) at the same temperature. The resulting solution was diluted with EtOH (1 mL) and a suspension of NaBH₄ (2 equiv.) in EtOH (2 mL) was then added drop-wise. The mixture was stirred at –40 °C for 30 min and quenched with H₂O (10 mL). The aqueous phase was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over MgSO₄, filtered, concentrated under reduced pressure and the crude product purified by flash column chromatography (hexane:EtOAc, 60:40).

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- [12] For details, see SI. While still premature, the superior performance of diaryl catalysts **3** and **4**, with respect to the dialkyl catalyst **5**, might be indicative of π - π interactions between the catalysts **3/4** and the arylsulfonyl moiety of substrates being operative.
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- [20] Current catalytic asymmetric Michael reaction protocols in which adducts with either *syn* or *anti* relative configuration can be formed tend to show, with few exceptions, moderate levels of diastereocontrol (see Ref 7). While results in Tables 1 and 2 confirm this inherent problem, we have found that improved dr values are affordable by changing the nature of the sulfone group. For instance, starting from the respective tert-butyl sulfone analogue to **17** and **20**, respectively, and propanal, lactones **22a** and **22d** were obtained in 90:10 and 85:15 diastereomeric ratio

